

Srinivas University

College of Social Science and Humanities

From,

Dr. Laveena D'Mello
Dean and Professor,
College of Social Sciences and Humanities,
Srinivas University, City Campus,
Pandeshwar, Mangaluru- 575001.

To,

Prof. Sachin
University College
Mangalore University,
Mangaluru- 575001.

Sub: To participate in BOS meeting of CSSH- Course BA Journalism and Mass Communication

Greetings from College of Social Sciences and Humanities!

We would like to request you to participate in our Board of Studies meeting which will be conducted **on February 2nd, Wednesday 2022 at 2.30 p.m.** at room no 4, at College of Social Sciences, Srinivas University. Kindly find the attached agenda below.

Agenda

1. To Approve the BA Journalism and Mass Communication course pattern
2. Identifying the subjects.
3. Value added courses
4. The syllabus as per NEP
5. Rules and regulation
6. Internal and External Paper setters
7. Valuation
8. Any other matter

Your participation will be highly appreciable. Please present on time. The rules and regulations which we have planned are attached with this letter. The new syllabus as Per NEP is prepared. Kindly go through it and note if any changes are required. So that we can discuss and approve during the meeting. Hope you will actively participate in the meeting.

Thanking you.

Yours Sincerely,

Dr. LaveenaD'Mello
Dean& Professor,
College of Social Sciences and Humanities,
Srinivas University, City Campus,
Pandeshwar, Mangaluru- 575001.

Date: 24th January, 2022

Place: Mangalore

Copy of the letter to;

1. Prof. Shushmitha
2. Dr. Pradeep M.D.
3. Dr. Vidya N
4. Ms. Ashwini
5. Ms. Sharanya
6. Prof. Sachin

Srinivas University

College of Social Science and Humanities

The report of the Board of Studies of BA Journalism and Mass Communication course was conducted on **February 2nd, Wednesday 2022 at 2.30 p.m** at room no 4, at College of Social Sciences, Srinivas University.

The following members were present for the meeting

Sl.No.	Name	Designation	Signature
1.	Dr. Laveena D'Mello	Chairperson	
2.	Prof. Shushmitha	Internal Member	
3.	Dr. Pradeep M.D.	Internal Member	
4.	Dr. Vidya N.	Internal Member	
5.	Ms. Ashwini	External Member	
6.	Ms. Sharanya	External Member	
7.	Prof. Sachin	External Member	

During the meeting the introduction of the course was done by the dean of the college Dr. Laveena D'Mello for the committee. And many issues related to new syllabus was discussed. The following resolutions were also taken. Meeting was conducted as per the Agenda.

Agenda

1. To Approve the BA Journalism and Mass Communication course pattern
2. Identifying the subjects.
3. Value added courses
4. The syllabus as per NEP
5. Rules and regulation

6. Internal and External Paper setters
7. Valuation
8. Any other matter

1. **To approve the new Course:** First and foremost the new course to approve the BA Journalism and Mass Communication course pattern as per NEP. As Per NEP, the first year as Certificate course, Second year Diploma, third year Degree and fourth year Honors and fifth year Master degree. Syllabus and subjects were identified and the whole course was planned accordingly. The syllabus was shared with the committee well in advance and discussion was started. And following resolution were taken.

Resolutions:

- i. The number of credits- 04 Approved.
- ii. Number of Lecture hours- 40 Hours Approved.
- iii. Mode of Delivery- Classroom mode/ Blended mode/Online Mode/Campus Networking Based was approved.
- iv. Course objectives- Approved.
- v. Teaching learning process and Padagogy – Lecture, Assignments, Individual and group presentations were Approved.
- vi. Learning Outcome- Approved.
- vii. Course Evaluation- Approved.
- viii. Title -Corrections made and approved.
- ix. Course Code- Approved.
- x. Unit wise division – (Five units each) and course contents- scrutiny done and approved.
- xi. Books for Reference- End of each subject’s books were suggested in the syllabus and those were approved.

So complete three years syllabus was brought to the notice of the board and subject for four years were identified and resolutions were made and approved by the BOS members.

2. **Identifying the subjects:** The various university syllabus was studied and relevant subjects were identified so that there will not be any overlapping of the subjects for Integrated Masters course.

Resolutions: All subjects were studied thoroughly and same was accepted by the BOS. The list of the subject is given below

SEMESTER I:

(Scheme attachment 1A)

3. **Value added courses:** Value added courses were identified in every semester and same was highlighted in the syllabus.

Resolution: All value added courses semester wise were approved during the meetings

4. The syllabus as per NEP: The new syllabus was drafted as per NEP including all value added courses, languages, and mode of delivery all was approved.

Resolution: Committee approved the complete syllabus of four years during the meeting.

5. Rules and regulation: There were changes in the rules and regulations as per NEP. Course Regulation Handbook of BSW course with programme outcomes (PO's) Programme Specific Outcomes (PSOs) and Course Outcomes (Cos) of the Programmes were shared.

Resolution: Resolution was passed and approved all course with programme outcomes (PO's) Programme Specific Outcomes (PSOs) and Course Outcomes (Cos) of the BSW Programmes.

6. **Internal and External Paper setters:** The list of the internal and external paper setters list was proposed during the meeting. The list of the identified BOE members will inform and take their consent by issuing the consent form.

Resolution: the list of the members was approved and asked to take their consent.

7. **Internal Assessment:** Outline for continuous assessment activities was shared and the patten was given.

Resolution: the outline approved in the BOS was as follows;

Activities	C1	C2	Total Marks
Session Test	10%	10%	20%
Seminars/Presentations/Activity	10%		10%
Casestudy/Assignment/Projectworketc.		10%	10%
Attendance		10%	10%
Total	20%	30%	50%

	arks	ks	
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At the end of each semester, examinations will be conducted for all the papers to be covered in that semester and evaluation will be done for 50 marks each. The timings of the examination will be followed as per academic calendar.

8. Pattern of Question Paper in End Semester Examination:

The question paper pattern in each Semester Exam for 50 marks consists of Objective type questions 6 questions all to answer (6 marks), Very short answer three questions out of four questions (6 marks) Seven marks questions 4 out of 5 questions (28 marks) , and one long essay of 10 marks out of two (10 marks).

No.ofQuestion	Type	Question/Mark	Total
6 out of 6	Objective type	6 x 1 = 06	06
3 out of 4	Very short	3 x 2= 06	06
4 out of 5	Short essay	4 x 7 = 28	28
1 out of 2	Long essay	1 x 10 =10	10
Total Semester Marks			50

9. **Any other matter:** After the general discussion about the NEP and the process of implementation it was decided to implement syllabus as per NEP. All have to work in hand in hand with other departments in providing the choice base subjects, so that students will benefit maximum. The meeting was ended at 6.00 pm with formal vote of thanks by the chair person Dr. Laveena DMello.

Semester wise Subjects details

SEMESTER I: Bachelor of Arts (BA Journalism and Mass Communication)

SN	Code	Title of Course	Teaching hours				Practical sessions/ Self/Study (S)	Exam			Credits
			Lecture(L)	Tutorial	Practical (P)	Total Hrs		Internal	External	Total	
1	21BAJ01	Fundamentals of Journalism (DSC)	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	4
2	21BAJ02	Reporting (DSC)	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	4
3	21BAJ03 (A)	Open Elective-1 (OE) Early Childhood Development	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	4
	21BAJ03 (B)	Open Elective-2 (OE) Principles of Management									
4	21BAJ04	Field Practicum – I Media Visit (DSC)	-	8	32	40	-	50	50	100	4
5	21BAJ05	Fundamentals of Communication I (E) (AECC)	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	3
6	21BAJ06	Kannada I (AECC)	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	3

	K										
	21BAJ06	Hindi I (AECC)									
	H										
	21BAJ06	Malayalam I (AECC)									
	M										
	21BAJ06	Online Mode I (AECC)									
	O										
7	21BAJ07	Digital Proficiency I (SEC)	-			20	-	50	-	50	2
8	21BAJ08	Health & Wellness (SEC)	20			20	-	50	-	50	2
9	21BAJ09	Basics of Nutrition (SEC)	20			20	-	50	-	50	2
10	21BAJ10	CommunicativeKannada	-	-	-	-	20	-	-	-	-
	Total					300				750	28

*DSC- Discipline

*DSC- Discipline Elective

*OE -open Elective

*SEC – Skilled

Enhancement CoursesAECC- Ability Enhancement Compulsory Course

SEMESTER II: Bachelor of Arts (BA Journalism and Mass Communication)

Sl. No.	Code	Title of Course	Teaching hours			Total Hrs	Practical sessions/Self/Study (S)	Exam			Credits
			Lecture(L)	Tutorial	Practical (P)			Internal	External	Total	
1	21BAJ11	Editing (DSC)	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	4
2	21BAJ12	Radio Broadcasting	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	4
3	21BAJ13 (A)	Open Elective-1 (OE) Human Resource Management	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	4
	21BAJ13 (B)	Open Elective-2 (OE) Youth Development through Social Work									
4	21BAJ14	Field Practicum – II Event Reporting (DSC)	-	8	32	40	-	50	50	100	4
5	21BAJ15	Fundamentals of Communication II (E) (AECC)	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	3
6	21BAJ16 K	Kannada II (AECC)	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	3
	21BAJ16 H	Hindi II (AECC)									
	21BAJ16 M	Malayalam II (AECC)									
	21BAJ16 O	Online Mode II (AECC)									
7	21BAJ17	Digital Proficiency II (SEC)	-	-	-	20	-	50	-	50	2
8	21BAJ18	NSS (SEC)	20	-	-	20	-	50	-	50	2
9	21BAJ19	Life Skills (SEC)	20	-	-	20	-	50	-	50	2
10	21BAJ20	CommunicativeKannada	-	-	-	-	20	-	-	-	-
Total						320				750	28

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*DSC- Discipline Elective

*OE -open Elective

*SEC – Skilled Enhancement Courses AECC- Ability Enhancement

Compulsory Course

SEMESTER III: Bachelor of Arts (BA Journalism and Mass Communication)

Sl. No.	Code	Title of Course	Teaching hours			Total Hrs	Practical sessions/Self/Study (S)	Exam			Credits
			Lecture(L)	Tutorial	Practical (P)			Internal	External	Total	
1	21BAJ21	Print Journalism (DSC)	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	4
2	21BAJ22	Advertisement (DSC)	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	4
3	21BAJ23 (A)	Open Elective-1 (OE)Disaster Management	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	4
	21BAJ23 (B)	Open Elective-2 (OE) Management Information system									
4	21BAJ24	Field Practicum – III Media Advertisement (DSC)	-	8	32	40	-	50	50	100	4
5	21BAJ25	Functional English-I (E) (AECC)	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	3
6	21BAJ26 K	Kannada III (AECC)	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	3
	21BAJ26 H	Hindi III (AECC)									
	21BAJ26 M	Malayalam III (AECC)									
	21BAJ26 O	Online Mode III (AECC)									
7	21BAJ27	Cyber Crime and Security (SEC)	-	-	-	20	-	50	-	50	2
8	21BAJ28	Games (SEC)	20	-	-	20	-	50	-	50	2
9	21BAJ29	Waste Management (SEC)	20	-	-	20	-	50	-	50	2
10	21BAJ30	CommunicativeKannada	-	-	-	-	20	-	-	-	-
Total						320				750	28

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*DSC- Discipline Elective

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AECC- Ability Enhancement

Compulsory Course

SEMESTER IV: Bachelor of Arts (BA Journalism and Mass Communication)

Sl. No.	Code	Title of Course	Teaching hours			Total Hrs	Practical sessions/Self/Study (S)	Exam			Credits
			Lecture(L)	Tutorial	Practical (P)			Internal	External	Total	
1	21BAJ31	Electronic Journalism (DSC)	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	4
2	21BAJ32	New Media Technology (DSC)	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	4
3	21BAJ33 (A)	Open Elective-1 (OE) Social Work Research	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	4
	21BAJ33 (B)	Open Elective-2 (OE)E- Business									
4	21BAJ34	Field Practicum – IV Anchoring (DSC)	-	8	32	40	-	50	50	100	4
5	21BAJ35	Functional English-II (E) (AECC)	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	3
6	21BAJ36 K	Kannada IV (AECC)	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	3
	21BAJ36 H	Hindi IV (AECC)									
	21BAJ36 M	Malayalam IV (AECC)									
	21BAJ36 O	Online Mode IV (AECC)									
7	21BAJ37	Entrepreneurship Start up (SEC)	-	-	-	20	-	50	-	50	2
8	21BAJ38	Yoga (SEC)	20	-	-	20	-	50	-	50	2
9	21BAJ39	Indian Constitution (SEC)	20	-	-	20	-	50	-	50	2
10	21BAJ40	CommunicativeKannada	-	-	-	-	20	-	-	-	-
		Total					320			750	28

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Compulsory Course

SEMESTER V: Bachelor of Arts (BA Journalism and Mass Communication)

Sl. No.	Code	Title of Course	Teaching hours				Practical sessions/Self/Study (S)	Exam			Credits
			Lecture(L)	Tutorial	Practical (P)	Total Hrs		Internal	External	Total	
1	21BAJ41	Public Relation (DSC)	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	4
2	21BAJ42	Film Production (DSC)	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	4
3	21BAJ43 (A)	Open Elective-1 (OE)Health care	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	4
	21BAJ43 (B)	Open Elective-2 (OE) Entrepreneur ship Development									
4	21BAJ44	Field Practicum – V Documentary film (DSC)	-	8	32	40	-	50	50	100	4
5	21BAJ45	Auditing techniques (AECC)	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	3
6	21BAJ46	Excel and SPSS	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	3
7	21BAJ47	Television Production (SEC)	-	-	-	20	-	50	-	50	2
8	21BAJ48	Music/Dance (SEC)	20	-	-	20	-	50	-	50	2
9	21BAJ49	Street Play (SEC)	20	-	-	20	-	50	-	50	2
Total						300				750	28

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AECC- Ability Enhancement

Compulsory Course

SEMESTER VI: Bachelor of Arts (BA Journalism and Mass Communication)

Sl. No.	Code	Title of Course	Teaching hours			Total Hrs	Practical sessions/Self/Study (S)	Exam			Credits
			Lecture (L)	Tutorial	Practical (P)			Internal	External	Total	
1	21BAJ51	Internship & Dissertation to produce News Magazine & Viva-Voce (SEC)	-	8	320	320	-	Internal Assessment Field practicum + Project 150 +150 = 300	External Assessment Field practicum + Project 150 +150 = 300 Viva-Voce exam = 150	750	28

SEMESTER VII: Bachelor of Arts (BA Journalism and Mass Communication)

Sl. No.	Code	Title of Course	Teaching hours			Total Hrs	Practical sessions/Self/Study (S)	Exam			Credits
			Lecture (L)	Tutorial	Practical(P)			Internal	External	Total	
1	21BAJ61	Communication Research Methods and Application (DSC)	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	4
2	21BAJ62	Media Law and Ethics (DSC)	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	4
3	21BAJ63	Magazine and Photo Journalism(DSC)	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	4
4	21BAJ64	Project – TV & Radio			200	200		350	100	450	16

SEMESTER VIII: Bachelor of Arts (BA Journalism and Mass Communication)

Sl. No.	Code	Title of Course	Teaching hours			Total Hrs	Practical sessions/Self/Study (S)	Exam			Credits
			Lecture(L)	Tutorial	Practical(P)			Internal	External	Total	
1	21BAJ71	Development Communication (DSC)	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	4
2	21BAJ72	Marketing Communication (DSC)	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	4
3	21BAJ73	Case Studies (DSC)	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	4
4	21BAJ74	Dissertation			200	200		350	100	450	16

Date:02/02/2022

Place: Mangalore

R.19 Semester wise Subjects details

SEMESTER I: Bachelor of Arts (BA Journalism and Mass Communication)

Sl. No.	Code	Title of Course	Teaching hours				Total Hrs	Practical sessions/Self/Study (S)	Exam			Credits
			Lecture (L)	Tutorial	Practical (P)	Internal			External	Total		
1	21BAJ01	Fundamentals of Journalism (DSC)	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	4	
2	21BAJ02	Reporting (DSC)	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	4	
3	21BAJ03 (A)	Open Elective-1 (OE) Early Childhood Development	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	4	
	21BAJ03 (B)	Open Elective-2 (OE) Principles of Management										
4	21BAJ04	Field Practicum – I Media Visit (DSC)	-	8	32	40	-	50	50	100	4	
5	21BAJ05	Fundamentals of Communication I (E) (AECC)	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	3	
6	21BAJ06 K	Kannada I (AECC)	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	3	
	21BAJ06 H	Hindi I (AECC)										
	21BAJ06 M	Malayalam I (AECC)										
	21BAJ06 O	Online Mode I (AECC)										
7	21BAJ07	Digital Proficiency I (SEC)	-			20	-	50	-	50	2	
8	21BAJ08	Health & Wellness (SEC)	20			20	-	50	-	50	2	
9	21BAJ09	Basics of Nutrition (SEC)	20			20	-	50	-	50	2	
10	21BAJ10	CommunicativeKannada	-	-	-	-	20	-	-	-	-	
		Total				300				750	28	

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SEMESTER II: Bachelor of Arts (BA Journalism and Mass Communication)

Sl. No.	Code	Title of Course	Teaching hours				Practical sessions/Self/Study (S)	Exam			Credits
			Lecture (L)	Tutorial	Practical (P)	Total Hrs		Internal	External	Total	
1	21BAJ11	Editing (DSC)	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	4
2	21BAJ12	Radio Broadcasting	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	4
3	21BAJ13 (A)	Open Elective-1 (OE) Human Resource Management	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	4
	21BAJ13 (B)	Open Elective-2 (OE) Youth Development through Social Work									
4	21BAJ14	Field Practicum – II Event Reporting (DSC)	-	8	32	40	-	50	50	100	4
5	21BAJ15	Fundamentals of Communication II (E) (AECC)	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	3
6	21BAJ16 K	Kannada II (AECC)	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	3
	21BAJ16 H	Hindi II (AECC)									
	21BAJ16 M	Malayalam II (AECC)									
	21BAJ16 O	Online Mode II (AECC)									
7	21BAJ17	Digital Proficiency II (SEC)	-			20	-	50	-	50	2
8	21BAJ18	NSS (SEC)	20			20	-	50	-	50	2
9	21BAJ19	Life Skills (SEC)	20			20	-	50	-	50	2
10	21BAJ20	CommunicativeKannada	-	-	-	-	20	-	-	-	-
		Total					320			750	28

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SEMESTER III: Bachelor of Arts (BA Journalism and Mass Communication)

Sl. No.	Code	Title of Course	Teaching hours				Practical sessions/Self/Study (S)	Exam			Credits
			Lecture (L)	Tutorial	Practical (P)	Total Hrs		Internal	External	Total	
1	21BAJ21	Print Journalism (DSC)	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	4
2	21BAJ22	Advertisement (DSC)	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	4
3	21BAJ23 (A)	Open Elective-1 (OE) Disaster Management	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	4
	21BAJ23 (B)	Open Elective-2 (OE) Management Information system									
4	21BAJ24	Field Practicum – III Media Advertisement (DSC)	-	8	32	40	-	50	50	100	4
5	21BAJ25	Functional English-I (E) (AECC)	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	3
6	21BAJ26 K	Kannada III (AECC)	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	3
	21BAJ26 H	Hindi III (AECC)									
	21BAJ26 M	Malayalam III (AECC)									
	21BAJ26 O	Online Mode III (AECC)									
7	21BAJ27	Cyber Crime and Security (SEC)	-	-	-	20	-	50	-	50	2
8	21BAJ28	Games (SEC)	20	-	-	20	-	50	-	50	2
9	21BAJ29	Waste Management (SEC)	20	-	-	20	-	50	-	50	2
10	21BAJ30	CommunicativeKannada	-	-	-	-	20	-	-	-	-
Total						320				750	28

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AECC- Ability Enhancement Compulsory Course

SEMESTER IV: Bachelor of Arts (BA Journalism and Mass Communication)

Sl. No.	Code	Title of Course	Teaching hours			Total Hrs	Practical sessions/Self/Study (S)	Exam			Credits
			Lecture (L)	Tutorial	Practical (P)			Internal	External	Total	
1	21BAJ31	Electronic Journalism (DSC)	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	4
2	21BAJ32	New Media Technology (DSC)	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	4
3	21BAJ33 (A)	Open Elective-1 (OE) Social Work Research	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	4
	21BAJ33 (B)	Open Elective-2 (OE) E- Business									
4	21BAJ34	Field Practicum – IV Anchoring (DSC)	-	8	32	40	-	50	50	100	4
5	21BAJ35	Functional English-II (E) (AECC)	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	3
6	21BAJ36 K	Kannada IV (AECC)	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	3
	21BAJ36 H	Hindi IV (AECC)									
	21BAJ36 M	Malayalam IV (AECC)									
	21BAJ36 O	Online Mode IV (AECC)									
7	21BAJ37	Entrepreneurship Start up (SEC)	-	-	-	20	-	50	-	50	2
8	21BAJ38	Yoga (SEC)	20	-	-	20	-	50	-	50	2
9	21BAJ39	Indian Constitution (SEC)	20	-	-	20	-	50	-	50	2
10	21BAJ40	CommunicativeKannada	-	-	-	-	20	-	-	-	-
Total						320				750	28

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AECC- Ability Enhancement Compulsory Course

SEMESTER V: Bachelor of Arts (BA Journalism and Mass Communication)

Sl. No.	Code	Title of Course	Teaching hours			Total Hrs	Practical sessions/Self/Study (S)	Exam			Credits
			Lecture (L)	Tutorial	Practical (P)			Internal	External	Total	
1	21BAJ41	Public Relation (DSC)	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	4
2	21BAJ42	Film Production (DSC)	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	4
3	21BAJ43 (A)	Open Elective-1 (OE) Health care	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	4
	21BAJ43 (B)	Open Elective-2 (OE) Entrepreneur ship Development									
4	21BAJ44	Field Practicum – V Documentary film (DSC)	-	8	32	40	-	50	50	100	4
5	21BAJ45	Auditing techniques (AECC)	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	3
6	21BAJ46	Excel and SPSS	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	3
7	21BAJ47	Television Production (SEC)	-	-	-	20	-	50	-	50	2
8	21BAJ48	Music/Dance (SEC)	20	-	-	20	-	50	-	50	2
9	21BAJ49	Street Play (SEC)	20	-	-	20	-	50	-	50	2
		Total					300			750	28

*DSC- Discipline

*DSC- Discipline Elective

*OE -open Elective

*SEC – Skilled Enhancement Courses

AECC- Ability Enhancement Compulsory Course

SEMESTER VI: Bachelor of Arts (BA Journalism and Mass Communication)

Sl. No.	Code	Title of Course	Teaching hours				Practical sessions/Self/Study (S)	Exam			Credits
			Lecture (L)	Tutorial	Practical (P)	Total Hrs		Internal	External	Total	
1	21BAJ51	Internship & Dissertation to produce a News Magazine & Viva-Voce (SEC)	-	8	320	320	-	Internal Assessment Field practicum + Project 150 +150 = 300	External Assessment Field practicum + Project 150 +150 = 300 Viva-Voce exam = 150	750	28

SEMESTER VII: Bachelor of Arts (BA Journalism and Mass Communication)

Sl. No.	Code	Title of Course	Teaching hours				Practical sessions/Self/Study (S)	Exam			Credits
			Lecture (L)	Tutorial	Practical (P)	Total Hrs		Internal	External	Total	
1	21BAJ61	Communication Research Methods and Application (DSC)	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	4
2	21BAJ62	Media Law and Ethics (DSC)	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	4
3	21BAJ63	Magazine and Photo Journalism(DSC)	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	4
4	21BAJ64	Project – TV & Radio			200 HRS	200 HRS		350	100	450	16

EMESTER VIII: Bachelor of Arts (BA Journalism and Mass Communication)

Sl. No.	Code	Title of Course	Teaching hours				Practical sessions/Self/Study (S)	Exam			Credits
			Lecture (L)	Tutorial	Practical (P)	Total Hrs		Internal	External	Total	
1	21BAJ71	Development Communication (DSC)	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	4
2	21BAJ72	Marketing Communication (DSC)	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	4
3	21BAJ73	Case Studies (DSC)	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	4
4	21BAJ74	Dissertation			200 HRS	200 HRS		350	100	450	16

